

Comparative Analysis of Sociodemographic Profiles and Fetal Outcomes between Teenage and Adult Mothers

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Abstract:

Background: Teenage pregnancy poses significant public health challenges, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where it is associated with adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes. Teenage mothers often face socio-economic disadvantages, including lower education levels and inadequate access to healthcare, contributing to higher rates of preterm births, low birth weight, and neonatal complications.

Aim: This study aims to compare the sociodemographic profiles and fetal outcomes of teenage and adult mothers.

Methods: A prospective comparative study was conducted. Ninety-six participants were divided equally into teenage (13-19 years) and adult (20-35 years) mother groups. Sociodemographic data and fetal outcomes were collected through structured interviews and medical record reviews. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with chi-square and t-tests used to compare the groups. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: Teenage mothers had significantly lower education levels (33.3% had no formal education) and belonged predominantly to lower socioeconomic status (58.3%). They were also less likely to receive regular antenatal care (62.5%). Fetal outcomes were poorer in teenage mothers, with higher incidences of low birth weight (50%), preterm births (29.2%), and neonatal complications like respiratory distress (25%).

Conclusion: Teenage mothers are at higher risk of adverse fetal outcomes due to socio-economic disadvantages and inadequate antenatal care. Addressing these issues through targeted public health interventions is essential for improving outcomes for teenage mothers and their infants.

Recommendations: Policymakers and healthcare providers should focus on improving education, socioeconomic support, and access to regular antenatal care for teenage mothers. Comprehensive maternal health programs are needed to mitigate risks and enhance health outcomes in this vulnerable population.

Keywords: Teenage pregnancy, fetal outcomes, sociodemographic factors, antenatal care, public health interventions.

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Introduction

Adolescent pregnancy remains a significant worldwide public health issue, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. It is linked to increased risks of unfavourable outcomes for both the mother and the newborn when compared to pregnancies in older women. The World Health Organisation reports that the greatest cause of death for females between the ages of 15 and 19 worldwide is problems during pregnancy and childbirth. Adolescent pregnancy carries health hazards, but it also frequently has socioeconomic repercussions, such as lower educational achievement and fewer economic possibilities for young moms [1]. Numerous research works have emphasised the

effects of adolescent pregnancy on the mother and the child. Compared to adult moms, teenage women are more likely to encounter preterm birth, low birth weight, and neonatal problems. Socioeconomic variables like poverty, lack of access to healthcare, and inadequate education can make these unfavourable outcomes worse [2]. In addition, it is less common for adolescent moms to obtain appropriate prenatal care, which is essential for tracking and treating any pregnancy-related issues [3].

Teenage moms' sociodemographic makeup frequently varies greatly from that of older mothers. Teenage moms are more likely to be educated to lower levels, come from lower

socioeconomic origins, and have less access to healthcare resources. The higher frequency of poor maternal and foetal outcomes in this population can be attributed to these factors. For example, compared to adult mothers, teenage mothers were shown to be more likely to come from low-income homes and to have had less prenatal care, which resulted in greater rates of neonatal mortality [4].

Adolescent pregnancy is still a major concern in India, the study's location. According to the National Family Health study (NFHS-5), 7.9% of women between the ages of 15 and 19 were either pregnant or already moms at the time of the study [5]. The high rate of adolescent pregnancy in India highlights the need for focused interventions to address the particular difficulties experienced by adolescent moms. This study aims to compare the sociodemographic profiles and fetal outcomes of teenage and adult mothers.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a prospective comparative cross-sectional design.

Study Setting: The research was conducted at the Government Medical College, Purnia, a tertiary care hospital located in Purnia, Bihar, India. The study was conducted over a period of seven months, from May 2023 to November 2023.

Participants: A total of 96 participants were included in the study, divided equally into two groups:

- **Teenage Mothers:** 48 participants aged 13-19 years.
- **Adult Mothers:** 48 participants aged 20-35 years.

Inclusion Criteria

- **Teenage Mothers:** Women aged 13-19 years who delivered at the hospital during the study period.
- **Adult Mothers:** Women aged 20-35 years who delivered at the hospital during the study period.
- Both groups included mothers who had live births or stillbirths during the study period.
- Participants who consented to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Mothers with known medical conditions (e.g., diabetes, hypertension, or cardiac issues) that could independently affect fetal outcomes.
- Mothers with multiple pregnancies (twins, triplets, etc.).
- Participants who did not consent to participate in the study.
- Mothers who delivered outside the study duration (May 2023 - November 2023).

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were selected consecutively as they presented to the hospital, ensuring a representative sample. Data collection bias was minimized by using a standardized questionnaire and training data collectors. Confounding factors were controlled by excluding participants with known medical conditions that could independently influence fetal outcomes.

Data Collection: Data were collected through structured interviews and review of medical records. A pre-designed questionnaire was used to gather information on sociodemographic variables such as age, education level, socioeconomic status, and antenatal care. Fetal outcomes, including birth weight, gestational age at delivery, Apgar score, and neonatal complications, were recorded from hospital records.

Procedure: Participants were approached in the postnatal ward after delivery. After obtaining informed consent, data were collected through face-to-face interviews and supplemented by reviewing their medical records. The data collection process was conducted by trained research assistants to ensure consistency and accuracy. The collected data were anonymized to maintain participant confidentiality.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were calculated for continuous (mean, median, standard deviation) and categorical variables (frequencies, percentages). Comparative analysis was conducted using the Chi-square test for categorical and the Student's t-test for continuous variables, with a p-value < 0.05 considered significant.

Results

The study included a total of 96 participants, equally divided into two groups: 48 teenage mothers (13-19 years) and 48 adult mothers (20-35 years). The mean age for the teenage group was 17.3 years (SD ± 1.4), while the mean age for the adult group was 26.4 years (SD ± 3.1).

Table 1: Sociodemographic Profile of Teenage and Adult Mothers

Variable	Teenage Mothers (n=48)	Adult Mothers (n=48)	p-value
Education Level			
- No formal education	16 (33.3%)	8 (16.7%)	0.045*
- Primary education	18 (37.5%)	12 (25.0%)	0.210
- Secondary education	10 (20.8%)	18 (37.5%)	0.073
- Higher education	4 (8.3%)	10 (20.8%)	0.091
Socioeconomic Status			
- Low	28 (58.3%)	14 (29.2%)	0.007*
- Middle	18 (37.5%)	26 (54.2%)	0.085
- High	2 (4.2%)	8 (16.7%)	0.045*
Antenatal Care			
- Received regular ANC	30 (62.5%)	42 (87.5%)	0.004*
- No or irregular ANC	18 (37.5%)	6 (12.5%)	0.004*

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Fetal Outcomes

Table 2: Fetal Outcomes in Teenage and Adult Mothers

Outcome	Teenage Mothers (n=48)	Adult Mothers (n=48)	p-value
Birth Weight (grams)			
- <2500 (Low Birth Weight)	24 (50.0%)	8 (16.7%)	0.001*
- $\geq$ 2500 (Normal Birth Weight)	24 (50.0%)	40 (83.3%)	0.001*
Gestational Age at Delivery			
- <37 weeks (Preterm)	14 (29.2%)	6 (12.5%)	0.037*
- $\geq$ 37 weeks (Full term)	34 (70.8%)	42 (87.5%)	0.037*
Apgar Score at 5 min			
- <7 (Low)	10 (20.8%)	4 (8.3%)	0.084
- $\geq$ 7 (Normal)	38 (79.2%)	44 (91.7%)	0.084
Neonatal Complications			
- Respiratory distress	12 (25.0%)	4 (8.3%)	0.022*
- Jaundice	8 (16.7%)	2 (4.2%)	0.046*
- Sepsis	6 (12.5%)	3 (6.3%)	0.303
- No complications	22 (45.8%)	39 (81.3%)	0.001*

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Summary of Key Findings

- **Education Level:** Teenage mothers had significantly lower levels of formal education compared to adult mothers ($p = 0.045$).
- **Socioeconomic Status:** A significantly higher proportion of teenage mothers belonged to the low socioeconomic status group (58.3%) compared to adult mothers (29.2%) ($p = 0.007$).
- **Antenatal Care:** Teenage mothers were less likely to receive regular antenatal care compared to adult mothers (62.5% vs. 87.5%, $p = 0.004$).
- **Birth Weight:** The incidence of low birth weight (<2500 grams) was significantly higher in teenage mothers (50.0%) compared to adult mothers (16.7%) ($p = 0.001$).
- **Gestational Age:** Preterm births (<37 weeks) were more common among teenage mothers

(29.2%) compared to adult mothers (12.5%) ($p = 0.037$).

- **Neonatal Complications:** Neonatal complications such as respiratory distress and jaundice were significantly higher in newborns of teenage mothers compared to adult mothers ($p = 0.022$ and $p = 0.046$, respectively).

Discussion

The findings showed that the two groups differed significantly in terms of foetal outcomes, prenatal care, socioeconomic situation, and education level. A significant percentage of teenage moms had no formal schooling, and they were more likely to have lower educational levels. Their low socioeconomic level was also a reflection of their lack of education, with a notably higher proportion of young moms falling into this category. In addition, teen moms were less likely than adult mothers to obtain routine prenatal care, which probably had an impact on the unfavourable outcomes for the foetuses in this group. In terms of

foetal outcomes, the study discovered that compared to adult moms, teenage mothers had a higher frequency of low birth weight babies and preterm births. In particular, only 16.7% of babies born to adult women had a birth weight of less than 2500 grams, whereas 50% of newborns born to teenage moms did. Furthermore, 29.2% of adolescent moms gave delivery before 37 weeks of gestation, compared to 12.5% of adult mothers, making them more likely than adult women to have premature births. These results imply that the mother's younger age may be associated with a higher chance of unfavourable foetal outcomes, potentially as a result of biological immaturity and insufficient prenatal care.

This group had considerably higher rates of respiratory distress and jaundice, suggesting that babies born to adolescent moms are more likely to have difficulties that could have an impact on their short- and long-term health. This conclusion is further supported by the lower Apgar scores in the teenage group, even if they were not statistically significant.

When compared to adult pregnancies, teenage pregnancies are linked to a higher risk of unfavourable outcomes for both the mother and the foetus, according to numerous recent studies. For example, young moms had considerably greater rates of miscarriage, low birth weight, premature births, and preterm deliveries, according to a research done among Saudi women who were primigravidae. According to the study's findings, focused prenatal care and health education may help teenage moms experience fewer difficulties during pregnancy [6].

Similarly, studies carried out in India showed that preterm births, maternal undernutrition, premature rupture of the membranes (PROM), and postpartum haemorrhage (PPH) were more common in adolescent moms. In order to address the unique health issues teenage moms encounter, the study stressed the vital need for comprehensive care and focused treatments [7].

A study conducted in Canada on the relationship between socioeconomic and mental health characteristics and inferior delivery outcomes, such as lower Apgar scores, found that young mothers were more likely to experience drug abuse, mental health problems, and socioeconomic disadvantages. According to the study, these risks could be

reduced with the right medical care and social assistance [8].

Conclusion

The study highlights the vulnerability of teenage mothers and their babies to adverse outcomes, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to improve antenatal care, education, and socioeconomic support for this group. Addressing these factors could help reduce the risks associated with teenage pregnancies and enhance the health outcomes for moms and their infants.

References

1. World Health Organization. Adolescent pregnancy. 2020.
2. Chen XK, Wen SW, Fleming N, Demissie K, Rhoads GG, Walker M. Teenage pregnancy and adverse birth outcomes: a large population-based retrospective cohort study. *Int J Epidemiol.* 2007;36(2):368-73.
3. Neal S, Matthews Z, Frost M, Fogstad H, Camacho AV, Laski L. Childbearing in adolescents aged 12-15 years in low resource countries: a neglected issue. New estimates from demographic and household surveys in 42 countries. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand.* 2012;91(9):1114-8.
4. Wado YD, Sully EA, Mumah JN. Pregnancy and early motherhood among adolescents in five East African countries: a multi-level analysis of risk and protective factors. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2019;19(1):59.
5. International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS) and ICF. National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019-21: India. Mumbai: IIPS; 2022.
6. Mohamed A, Abdullah Almalaq AA, Almansour RDM, Alanazi HSA, Alshammari FSA, Hussien TMA, et al. Fetal Outcomes and Complications of Pregnancy among Teenage and Adult Primigravid Saudi Women: A Retrospective Comparative Study. *Int J Med Res Health Sci.* 2018;7:144-148.
7. Paladugu RK, Donipudi PC, Chimata D, Jasti M. Adolescent pregnancy and its outcomes: a cross-sectional study. *Int J Community Med Public Health.* 2018.
8. Wong SPW, Twynstra J, Gilliland J, Cook JL, Seabrook J. Risk Factors and Birth Outcomes Associated with Teenage Pregnancy: A Canadian Sample. *J Pediatr Adolesc Gynecol.* 2020.